

Systems based instantiation of the core gene regulatory network underlying epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition: the liver cancer case

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

It is quite obvious that chronic-degenerative human diseases (like Alzheimer’s Disease or Diabetes), are extremely complex biological phenomena. From a medical systems biology perspective, such organized complexity, that basically comes from the interplay between the environment and the gene regulatory dynamics that underlies the onset and progression of the disease, asks for the development of a mechanistic systems based approach intended to uncover the involved robust generic regulatory principles. This in order to bridge the unfortunate gap that exists between medical systems biology and medical clinical practice (see for instance Alvarez-Buylla et al (2018) and the references therein). In the specific context of the study of human epithelial cancer, recent studies built around the formal conceptualization of the stochastic epigenetic landscape (see Villarreal et al (2012)), have been successful when tackling the mechanistic uncovering of the phenotypic-plasticity generic principles that underlie the onset and progression of this disease at the cellular and tissue levels. Specifically, the core gene regulatory network that rules the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition, a key self-organized tissue-related morphogenetic process causally involved in the spontaneous immortalization of cells *in vitro*, has been characterized through the integration of

available high throughput experimental data via a formal mathematical and computer based approach (see Mendez et al (2017)). Such a bottom-up methodological perspective, that formalizes the underlying regulatory core into a discrete systems based qualitative representation of the finite set of logical rules that govern the dynamics of each of the network components as a function of the states of its regulators, is well placed to address the exploration of dynamical processes linked to patient’s lifestyle that potentiate the disease’s emergence. Here we extend that mathematical model to instantiate the liver cancer case, a quite complex phenomenon (see for instance Seshachalam et al (2018); Dang et al (2011) and the references therein) (see Figure 1). Thus, we characterize the cell phenotypic transitions that shape the attractors landscape state trajectories that define the transition from a normal epithelial cell profile to a stem-like cell phenotype with a potentially tumorigenic behavior via an intermediary cell senescent state. Our goal is then to prepare the ground to address the systems based development of preventive therapeutic interventions based on the application of formal state-based optimal control methodologies built around the re-design of the underlying stochastic epigenetic landscapes (build around the results exposed in Dávila-Velderrain et al (2015)). We are particularly interested in the design of control schemes based on the modulatory role that nutrition has on the inflammatory response (taking for this into account the core gene regulatory dynamics that rule this phenomenon, as exposed in Martínez-Sánchez et al (2018)). This because the rhythm of the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition phenomena causally depends on the dynamical inflammatory response activated by exogenous disturbances. We are also interested in the under-

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Fig. 1. **Epithelial-to-Mesenchymal transition in the context of liver cancer.** This figure shows the core gene regulatory network that drives the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition, instantiated to the liver cancer case. The depicted network has 44 nodes. Black lines correspond to the regulatory interactions that define the original core gene regulatory network. Red lines correspond to the new uncovered interactions that involve liver cancer regulatory dynamics. Green lines correspond to the regulatory interactions that link the hepatocyte dynamics with the nodes that belong to the original core gene regulatory network.

standing of the systems based consequences that the modulation of the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition has on the cell cycle behavior (see Ortiz-Gutiérrez et al (2015)). We must point that the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition phenomenon has recently attracted the attention of control systems theorists interested in cellular reprogramming, who developed quite interesting methodologies for both the analysis of the involved network and the control of its dynamical behavior (see for instance Gómez Tejeda Zañudo et al (2019); Al-Radhawi and Sontag (2020) and the references therein). However, the mathematical models that are usually considered in such studies significantly reduce the complexity of the involved network of nonlinear interactions (working then with a so-called generic small-size model). This because of the associated computational cost. It is quite obvious that realistic control strategies should take into account realistic mathematical models. Since the core gene regulatory network that underlies epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition in the context of liver cancer is connected to a complex set of non only regulatory networks (*e.g.* the network that rules the inflammatory behavior and the network that underlies the cell cycle, see for instance He and Karin (2011)) but also to metabolic networks and signaling pathways, realistic control strategies need to be developed in order to tackle the involved level of complexity. Fortunately the gene regulatory networks analysis toolbox grows constantly in quality and sophistication (see for instance the methodologies explored in Paulevé et al (2014)). Our modeling strategy is then aimed at providing realistic robust models, based on available experimental evidence, to the community of experts in mathematical systems theory.

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